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FUNCTIONAL RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN PARAMETERS OF URIC ACID EXCHANGE AND IMMUNITY IN FEMALE RATS

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ФУНКЦІОНАЛЬНІ ЗВ'ЯЗКИ МІЖ ПАРАМЕТРАМИ ОБМІНУ СЕЧОВОЇ КИСЛОТИ І ІМУНІТЕТУ У САМОК ЩУРІВ

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ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ СВЯЗИ МЕЖДУ ПАРАМЕТРАМИ ОБМЕНА МОЧЕВОЙ КИСЛОТЫ И ИММУНИТЕТА У КРЫС-САМОК

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Резюме/Summary

Background. Previously, we obtained in female rats a wide range of uric acid metabolism parameters, divided into four clusters, which quantitatively and qualitatively were different from each other. Because uric acid is identified as an endogenous adjuvant, that drives immune responses in the absence of microbial stimulation, in this article, functional relationships of uricemia and uricosuria with the parameters of immunity will be analyzed. *Material and Methods.* Experiment was performed on 58 healthy female Wistar rats 220-300 g. Among them, 10 animals remained intact, using tap water from drinking ad libitum. The rats of other groups have been administered various fluids through the tube for 6 days. The serum and urine levels of the uric acid

(uricase method) were determined. In the blood, the parameters of immunity were determined. From thymus and spleen made smears-imprints for counting splenocytogram and thymocytogram. For them, as well as leukocytogram, Shannon's entropy was calculated. *Results.* The analysis of the canonical correlation between the two parameters of uric acid metabolism, on one hand, and the parameters of immunity, on the other, conducted. It is found, that the causal canonical root receives a factor load from uricosuria twice than from uricemia. Judging by the factor loadings on the immune canonical root, the most significant enhancing effect of endogenous uric acid is increasing in the intensity and activity of the phagocytosis of microbes by neutrophils (except of monocytes) of blood. In addition, uric acid increases the relative content of lymphocytes, in general, and B-lymphocytes, in particular, in the blood and T-lymphocytes in the thymus. Less significant enhancing effect of uric acid on the increase in the content of fibroblasts in the spleen and macrophages in the thymus, as well as the increase in entropy of the immunocytogram of blood. On the other hand, uric acid significantly reduces the entropy of blood leukocytogram, the total blood content of leukocytes and the proportion of monocytes and young forms of neutrophils in leukocytogram as well as natural killer cells in immunocytogram. In addition, uric acid reduces the entropy of thymocytogram and the proportion of epitheliocytes and reticulocytes. Taken together, both parameters of uric acid metabolism determine the immunity status of healthy female rats by 71%. *Conclusion.* Endogenous uric acid exerts a modulatory immunotropic effect in healthy female rats.

Key Words: uricosuria, uricemia, immunity, relationships, female rats.

Передумова. Раніше ми отримали широкий спектр параметрів обміну сечової кислоти у щурів, розділений на чотири кластери, кількісно і якісно відмінні один від одного. Позаяк сечова кислота була ідентифікована як ендогенний ад'ювант, який стимулює імунну реакцію за відсутності мікробної стимуляції. У цій статті будуть проаналізовані функціональні зв'язки урикемії та урикозурії з параметрами імунітету. *Матеріал і методи.*

Експеримент проводили на 58 здорових щурах лінії Wistar масою 220-300 г. Серед них 10 тварин залишалися інтактними, вживаючи для пиття водопровідну воду *ad libitum*. Щурам інших груп протягом 6 днів вводили через трубку різні рідини. Визначали рівні сечової кислоти (уриказним методом) в сироватці та добовій сечі. У крові визначалися параметри імунітету. З тимусу та селезінки робили мазки-відбитки для підрахунку спленоцитограми та тимоцитограми. Для них, а також лейкоцитограми, розраховували ентропію Шеннона. *Результати.* Проведено аналіз канонічної кореляції між двома параметрами метаболізму сечової кислоти, з одного боку, та параметрами імунітету, з іншого. Встановлено, що причинний канонічний корінь отримує факторне навантаження від урикозурії вдвічі більше, ніж від урикемії. Судячи з факторних навантажень на імунний канонічний корінь, найзначнішим посилюючим ефектом ендогенної сечової кислоти є підвищення інтенсивності та активності фагоцитозу мікробів нейтрофілами (але не моноцитами) крові. Крім того, сечова кислота збільшує відносний вміст лімфоцитів в цілому та В-лімфоцитів зокрема, у крові та Т-лімфоцитів у тимусі. Менш вагомий посилюючий вплив сечової кислоти на збільшення вмісту фіброblastів у селезінці та макрофагів у вилочковій залозі, а також на збільшення ентропії імунітограм крові. З іншого боку, сечова кислота значно знижує ентропію лей-

коцитограми крові, загальний вміст лейкоцитів у крові та частку моноцитів та молодих форм нейтрофілів у лейкоцитогамі, а також природних кілерів в імунітограмі. Разом з тим, сечова кислота знижує ентропію тимоцитогамі та вміст в ній епітеліоцитів і ретикулоцитів, а також вміст еозинофілів у спленоцитогамі. У сукупності обидва параметри метаболізму сечової кислоти визначають стан імунітету здорових щурів на 71%. **Висновок.** Ендогенна сечова кислота чинить модулюючий імунотропний ефект у здорових щурів.

Ключові слова: урикозурія, урикемія, імунітет, зв'язки, самки щурів.

Предисловие. Ранее мы получили широкий спектр параметров обмена мочевой кислоты у крыс, которые разделили на четыре кластера, количественно и качественно отличающиеся один от другого. Так мочевая кислота была идентифицирована как эндогенный адъювант, который стимулирует иммунную реакцию в отсутствие микробной стимуляции. В этой статье будут проанализированы функциональные связи урикемии и урикозурии с параметрами иммунитета. *Материал и методы.* Эксперимент проводили на 58 здоровых крысах линии Wistar массой 220-300 г. Среди них 10 животных оставались интактными и употребляли для питья водопроводную воду ad libitum. Крысам других групп в течение 6 дней вводили через трубку разные жидкости. Определяли уровни мочевой кислоты (уриказным методом) в сыворотке и суточной моче. В крови определялись параметры иммунитета. Из тимуса и селезенки делали мазки-отпечатки для подсчета спленоцитогамы и тимоцитогамы. Для них, а также лейкоцитогамы, рассчитывали энтропию Шеннона. *Результаты.* Проведен анализ канонической корреляции между двумя параметрами метаболизма мочевой кислоты, с одной стороны, и параметрами иммунитета, с другой. Установлено, что причинный канонический корень получает факторную нагрузку от урикозурии вдвое больше, чем от урикемии. Судя по факторным нагрузкам на иммунный канонический корень, наиболее значимым усиливающим эффектом эндогенной мочевой кислоты является повышение интенсивности и активности фагоцитоза микробов нейтрофилами (но не моноцитами) крови. Кроме того, мочевая кислота увеличивает относительное содержание лимфоцитов в целом и В-лимфоцитов в частности, в крови и Т-лимфоцитов в тимусе. Менее весомый усиливающий влияние мочевой кислоты на увеличение содержания фибробластов в селезенке и макрофагов в вилочковой железе, а также на увеличение энтропии иммуноцитогамы крови. С другой стороны, мочевая кислота значительно снижает энтропию лейкоцитогамы крови, общее содержание лейкоцитов в крови и долю моноцитов и молодых форм нейтрофилов в лейкоцитогаме, а также натуральных киллеров в иммуноцитогаме. Вместе с тем, мочевая кислота снижает энтропию тимоцитогамы и содержание в ней эпителиоцитов и ретикулоцитов, а также содержание эозинофилов в спленоцитогаме. В совокупности оба параметра метаболизма мочевой кислоты определяют состояние иммунитета здоровых крыс на 71%. *Выводы.* Эндогенная мочевая кислота оказывает модулирующий иммунотропный эффект у здоровых крыс.

Ключевые слова: урикозурия, урикемия, иммунитет, связи, крысы-самки.

Introduction

Previously, we obtained in female rats a wide range of uric acid metabolism

parameters, divided into four clusters, quantitatively and qualitatively different from each other. On the basis of the ac-

cepted criteria, 29,3% of animals state normouricemia in combination with normal or slightly increased excretion of uric acid. In 24,1% of rats, hypouricemia is combined with normal or slightly reduced uricosuria. In 31,0% of animals normal or slightly elevated levels of plasma uric acid are accompanied by a very marked dispersion of uricosuria. The remaining 15,5% of rats expressed hyperuricemia combined with normal or slightly increased uricosuria [9]. Because uric acid has been identified as an endogenous adjuvant that drives immune responses in the absence of microbial stimulation [7], in this article, functional relationships of uricemia and uricosuria with the parameters of immunity will be analyzed.

Material And Methods

Experiment was performed on 58 healthy female Wistar rats 220-300 g. Among them 10 animals remained intact, using tap water from drinking ad libitum. The rats of other groups have been administered various fluids at a dose of 1,5 mL/100 g of body mass through the tube for 6 days.

The day after the completion of the drinking course in all rats, at first, a sample of peripheral blood (by incision of the tip of the tail) was taken for leukocytogram analysis. Animals were then placed in individual chambers with perforated bottom for collecting daily urine. The experiment was completed by decapitation of rats in order to collect as much blood as possible.

The serum and urine levels of the uric acid (uricase method) were determined. The analyzes were carried out according to the instructions described in the manual [8]. The analyzers "Pointe-180" ("Scientific", USA) were used with appropriate sets.

In the blood, the parameters of immunity were determined according to the tests of the 1st and 2nd levels of the

WHO, as described in the manual [12]: the relative content of the population of T-lymphocytes in a test of spontaneous rosette formation with erythrocytes of sheep, their theophylline-resistant (T-helper) and theophylline-sensitive (T-cytolytic) subpopulations (by the test of sensitivity of rosette formation to theophylline); the population of B-lymphocytes (by the test of complementary rosette formation with erythrocytes of sheep). Natural killers were identified as large granules contain lymphocytes.

About the state of the phagocytic function of neutrophils (microphages) and monocytes (macrophages) were judged by the phagocytic index, the microbial count and the killing index for *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC N25423 F49) [3, 5, 14, 16].

After decapitation, the spleen and thymus were removed from the animals. Immune organs weighed and made smears-imprints for counting splenocytogram and thymocytogram [1-3]. For them, as well as leukocytogram, Shannon's entropy was calculated [10, 15].

Digital material is statistically processed on a computer using the software package "Statistica 5.5".

Results And Discussion

According to calculations by the formula: $|r| = \frac{\exp[2t/(n-1,5)^{0,5}] - 1}{\exp[2t/(n-1,5)^{0,5}] + 1}$, for a sample of $n=58$ critical value $|r|$ at $p<0,05$ ($t>2,00$) is 0,26, at $p<0,02$ ($t>2,39$) is 0,31, at $p<0,01$ ($t>2,66$) is 0,34, at $p<0,001$ ($t>3,46$) is 0,43.

Screening of linear correlation coefficients between uricosuria and uricemia, on the one hand, and the recorded parameters of immunity, on the other hand, revealed the following. First of all, uricosuria is stronger than uricemia due to the parameters of immunity.

In particular, the maximum linear correlation coefficient was found between

uricosuria and microbial count of blood neutrophils ($r=0,54$; $R^2=0,292$). More precisely, the dependence is approximated by the fourth-order curve (Fig. 1).

Less commonly associated urocuria with a relative content of monocytes

in blood ($r=-0,44$; $R^2=0,194$). The relationship between them is clearly nonlinear (Fig. 2).

The effect of uricosuria on the relative blood content of natural killer cells is similar in strength ($r=-0,41$; $R^2=0,168$) (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. Scatterplot of correlation between Uricosuria (X-line) and Microbial Count of blood Neutrophils (Y-line)

Fig. 2. Scatterplot of correlation between Uricosuria (X-line) and blood level of Monocytes (Y-line)

Regression Summary for Uricosuria

$R = 0,768$; $R^2 = 0,590$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0,481$; $F_{(12)} = 5,4$; $p < 10^{-5}$

Variables	r	Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₄₅₎	p-level
Microbial Count Neutrophils	0,54	0,501	0,224	1,201	0,537	2,24	0,03
Lymphocytes Thymus, %	0,3	0,163	0,122	0,205	0,154	1,33	0,189
Macrophages Thymus, %	0,19	0,227	0,109	0,66	0,317	2,08	0,043
Fibroblastes Spleen, %	0,19	0,295	0,103	0,556	0,193	2,88	0,006
B Lymphocytes Blood, %	0,18	0,169	0,102	0,175	0,105	1,66	0,104
Entropy Immunocytogram	0,14	0,12	0,106	39,5	34,83	1,13	0,263
Monocytes Blood, %	-0,44	-0,468	0,316	-0,639	0,432	-1,48	0,146
Natural Killers Blood, %	-0,41	0,545	0,321	0,813	0,478	1,7	0,096
Eosinophiles Spleen, %	-0,34	-0,155	0,113	-0,611	0,446	-1,37	0,178
Stub Neutrophils Blood, %	-0,23	-0,173	0,104	-0,485	0,293	-1,66	0,105
Leukocytes Blood, 10 ⁹ /L	-0,18	-0,156	0,106	-0,11	0,074	-1,48	0,146
Basophiles Blood, %	-0,15	-0,152	0,104	-0,981	0,669	-1,47	0,15

Unlike the previous immune parameters, entropy of blood leukocytogram is associated with uricosuria with almost linear dependence ($r=-0,46$; $R^2=0,212$) (Fig. 4).

In addition, there is a significant positive correlation of uricosuria with phagocytic index of blood neutrophils ($r=0,31$), T-lymphocytes content in the thymocytogram ($r=0,30$) and pan-lymphocytes in blood leukocytogram ($r=0,29$) and negative correlation with the content in the thymocytogram of epitheliocytes ($r=-0,30$) and reticulocytes ($r=-0,27$), as well as with the entropy of thymocytogram ($r=-0,25$).

However, when constructing a regression model with the stepwise exclusion of six' mentioned parameters were out of the model, instead it has revealed some parameters of immunity with insignificant correlation coefficients (Table 1). This is probably due to the nonlinear nature of the relationships. Uricosuria was found to determine the immune status of female rats by 59% (Table 1 and Fig. 5).

Table 1

Fig. 3. Scatterplot of correlation between Uricosuria (X-line) and blood level of Natural Killer cells (Y-line)

Fig. 4. Scatterplot of correlation between Uricosuria (X-line) and the Entropy of Leukocytoqram (Y-line)

Uricemia is much weaker than uricosuria, determines the immune status of female rats by only 40% (Table 2 and Fig. 6), what is not included in the model

variability of these parameters in intact animals (0,939 and 0,516, respectively) [9].

Regression Summary for Uricemia
R=0,630; R²=0,396; Adjusted R²=0,252; F₍₁₁₎=2,7; p=0,008

	Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₄₆₎	p-level	
Variables	r	Intercept	-3873	10553	-0,37	0,715	
Monocytes Blood, %	-0,33	-1,022	0,385	-188,5	70,9	-2,66	0,011
Natural Killers Blood, %	-0,25	0,546	0,397	109,9	79,9	1,38	0,176
Reticulocytes Spleen, %	-0,24	-0,327	0,152	-80,9	37,6	-2,16	0,036
Entropy Thymocytogram	-0,21	0,692	0,473	10652	7288	1,46	0,151
Entropy Splenocytogram	-0,13	-0,462	0,267	-10607	6136	-1,73	0,091
Plasmocytes Spleen, %	-0,11	-0,18	0,166	-60,9	56	-1,09	0,282
Lymphocytes Thymus, %	0,2	0,933	0,488	158,9	83,2	1,91	0,062
Fibroblastes Spleen, %	0,13	0,18	0,135	45,8	34,3	1,34	0,188
Phagocytic Index Neutroph, %	0,12	-0,177	0,166	-20,5	19,3	-1,07	0,292
Reticulocytes Thymus, %	0,11	0,331	0,137	120,6	49,7	2,43	0,019
Lymphocytes Spleen, %	0,11	-0,444	0,279	-78,1	49,1	-1,59	0,118

association of uricemia with microbial count of blood neutrophils (r=0,26) and the content of Hassal's corpuscles in the thymocytogram (r=-0,31) as well as entropy of leukocytogram (r=-0,25), which also deserve attention.

This condition with determination seems quite logical, since uricemia, unlike uricosuria, reflects only the situational (biorhythmic) level of uric acid in the body.

At the final stage, an analysis of the canonical correlation between the two parameters of uric acid metabolism, on one hand, and the parameters of immunity, on the other, were conducted. It is found that the causal canonical root receives a factor load from uricosuria twice that from uricemia (Table 3). Interestingly, the factor loadings coincide quite well with the coefficients of

Judging by the factor loadings on the immune canonical root, the most significant enhancing effect of endogenous uric acid is increase in the intensity and activity of the phagocytosis of microbes by neutrophils (but not monocytes) of blood. In addition,

R=0,769; R²=0,591; $\chi^2_{(13)}=44$; p<10⁻⁴; Λ Prime=0,409
 Fig. 5. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Uricosuria (X-line) and the Immunity (Y-line) in female rats

R=0,629; R²=0,396; $\chi^2_{(11)}=25,5$; p=0,007; Λ Prime=0,604
 Fig. 6. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Uricemia (X-line) and the Immunity (Y-line) in female rats

R=0,844; R²=0,712; $\chi^2_{(46)}=77$; p=0,003; Λ Prime=0,175
 Fig. 7. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Uricosuria and Uricemia (X-line) and the Immunity (Y-line) in female rats

uric acid increases the relative content of lymphocytes in general and B-lymphocytes in particular in the blood and T-lymphocytes in the thymus. Less significant effect of uric acid on the increase in the content of fibroblasts in the spleen and macrophages in the thymus, as well as the increase in entropy of the immunocytogram of blood.

On the other hand, uric acid significantly reduces the entropy of blood leukocytogram, the total blood content of leukocytes and the proportion of monocytes and young forms of neutrophils in leukocytogram, as well as natural killer cells in immunocytogram. In addition, uric acid reduces the entropy of thymocytogram and the proportion of epitheliocytes and reticulocytes.

Unfortunately, the bone marrow cytogram was not investigated in this study. But, even without this, we have got the impression, that uric acid does not meet the classic characteristics of neither stressors nor antistressors.

Taken together, both parameters of uric acid metabolism determine the immunity status of healthy female rats by 71% (Fig. 7).

We consider, that it is appropriate to cite the results of long-standing clinical observations with the participation of one of the authors [13] regarding the effect of adaptation status on the strength and even the nature of correlating relationships of uricemia with

parameters of immunity. It was found that in individuals with normal adaptation status, classified as a harmonic general adaptation reaction, correlation with the activity and intensity of phagocytosis *Staph. aureus* by neutrophils is positive ($r=0,57$ and $0,20$, respectively), and with the monocyte site in the leukocytoqram and the total leukocyte count is negative ($r=-0,23$ and $-0,34$, respectively), which is consistent with our data in healthy

rats. In contrast, in individuals with premorbid (disharmonious) and pathologic general adaptation reactions the connections come to naught or reverse.

The negative nature of correlation of uricemia with the level in the immunocytoqram of natural killers found in healthy rats is confirmed in two groups of people with minimal suppression ($r=-0,32$ and $-0,19$); on the other hand, in cases of deeper suppression, the connection reverses ($r=+0,15$) [13].

The ambiguity of the effects of uric acid on phagocytosis and natural killer cells is also revealed in modern publications [4, 6, 7, 11].

Conformity To Ethical Standards

Experiments on animals have been carried out in accordance with the provisions of the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, revised and supplemented in 2002 by the Directives of the National

Committees for Ethics in Scientific Research.

The carrying out of experiments was approved by the Ethics Committee of the I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University. The modern rules for the maintenance and use of laboratory animals complying with the principles of the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for scientific experiments and needs are observed (Strasbourg, 1985).

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Table 3

Factor loads on canonical roots of uric acid metabolism and immunity parameters as well as correlation coefficients between them

Right set	R		
Uricosuria	-0,996		
Uricemia	-0,548	UrU	UrP
Left set	R	r	r
Microbial Count Neutrophils	-0,638	0,54	0,26
Phagocytic Index Neutroph, %	-0,36	0,31	0,12
Lymphocytes Thymus, %	-0,357	0,3	0,2
Pan-Lymphocytes Blood, %	-0,33	0,29	0,03
Fibroblastes Spleen, %	-0,229	0,19	0,13
Macrophages Thymus, %	-0,208	0,19	-0,06
B Lymphocytes Blood, %	-0,204	0,18	-0,03
Entropy Immunocytoqram	-0,168	0,14	0,1
Reticulocytes Spleen, %	-0,006	0,03	-0,24
Entropy Leukocytoqram	0,549	-0,46	-0,24
Monocytes Blood, %	0,538	-0,44	-0,33
Natural Killers Blood, %	0,496	-0,41	-0,25
Eosinophiles Spleen, %	0,393	-0,34	-0,07
Epitheliocytes Thymus, %	0,35	-0,3	-0,1
Entropy Thymocytoqram	0,305	-0,25	-0,21
Reticulocytes Thymus, %	0,289	-0,27	0,11
Stub Neutrophils Blood, %	0,27	-0,23	-0,12
Leukocytes Blood, 10 ⁹ /L	0,219	-0,18	-0,09
Basophiles Blood, %	0,166	-0,15	-0,03
Hassal's corpuscles Thymus, %	0,145	-0,1	-0,31
Entropy Splenocytoqram	0,132	-0,1	-0,13
Lymphocytes Spleen, %	0,024	-0,03	0,11
Plasmocytes Spleen, %	0,022	-0,01	-0,11

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